

Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Towards Cervical Cancer and Screening Amongst Female Healthcare Professionals in A Tertiary Care Centre, Madurai: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: Cervical cancer is the second most common cancer in India and leading cause for cancer related deaths among women in our country. Screening by Pap smear has reduced its incidence in developed countries but implementation of this screening technique has not been successful in developing countries.

Aim: To assess female healthcare professionals regarding their knowledge, attitude and practice towards cervical cancer and screening.

Methodology: This is a cross sectional study conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Velammal Medical College and Research Institute, Madurai from January 2024 to June 2024 among female healthcare professionals – doctors, nurses and Auxiliary Nursing Midwifery (ANM). A simple random sampling method was used for recruitment. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect the required data.

Results: Out of 332 participants majority were doctors 46.4%(154) remaining 30.1%(100) and 23.5%(78) were staff nurses and ANM. The mean age of study participants was 28.65 years. 54.8%(182) were married. 69.6%(231) and 20.8%(69) appeared to have good and fair level of knowledge respectively. 292 participants (88%) believed that cytology test is useful for detection of carcinoma cervix and 53 participants (16%) undergone screening test (Pap smear). Only 21.4% (71) have been vaccinated for HPV.

Conclusion: Our study population showed overall good and fair knowledge about cervical cancer and screening. However, only less than one fourth of the participants had undergone screening and HPV vaccination. Hence our study highlights the gap between knowledge and practice which has to be met by appropriate health education programs and mass campaign. Government should take initiatives for provision of HPV vaccines in a subsidiary price and also to include HPV vaccination in Indian immunization schedule.

Keywords: Cervical Cancer, Health Care Professional, Knowledge, HPV Vaccine, Attitude, Practice.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer among women throughout the world. [1] As per WHO the global incidence of cervical cancer was 6,60,000 and mortality was around 3,50,000 in the year 2022. The highest incidence and death rates are reported in Sub Saharan Africa, Central America & south East Asia (SEA). India carries one fourth of global burden and 70% of the SEA 's burden. [2] Next to breast cancer, cervical cancer is the most common cancer in India.

Carcinoma cervix and its precancerous lesions are mainly caused by human papilloma virus (HPV) infection which is sexually transmitted. [3,4] HPV 16 & 18 are most oncogenic serotypes which results in about 50% of High grade intra epithelial lesions (HSIL-Cervical Intraepithelial Neoplasia CIN 2 and 3). Usually HPV infection is cleared by our host immunity in an immuno competent individual. In case of persistent HPV infection with associated risk factors like sexually transmitted diseases (STD), HIV, multiple sexual partners,

early age of sexual intercourse, obesity, smoking there is more chance of transformation of precancerous lesions to invasive cancer. [5] It takes about 15-20yrs to undergo this transformation in an immuno competent individual. Hence we can utilize this golden period for screening in order to reduce the incidence of cervical cancer.

The precancerous lesions are usually asymptomatic or may rarely present with offensive vaginal discharge, chronic low back ache, inter menstrual or post coital bleeding. Cervical cancer is preventable and completely curable disease if diagnosed at an early stage by various screening tests. (Pap smear, co testing, HPV DNA testing, VIA). [6] Papanicolaou (PAP) smear is a renowned test to screen & diagnose early stage of cervical cancer. [7] 68% -84% of women are undergoing this screening test in developed countries but in India due to lack of public awareness, it is only 2.6%-5%. [8]As per several studies conducted in Nepal and other developing countries they found the following barriers for screening such as embarrassment, lack of counselling, not recommended by health care professionals ,no symptoms ,anxious feeling when the screening test becomes positive , fear of pain , no reason to undergo the test and not aware of the benefits of screening. [9-14] In order to improve the cervical cancer screening rates, health care professionals should have adequate awareness about the disease, preventive strategies and treatment modalities because they are the decision makers regarding performance of screening test along with the patient. [15,16,17]

Important preventive strategy is administration of HPV vaccine. Currently Gardasil, Gardasil [9], Cervarix HPV vaccines are available in India. Both Gardasil & Cervarix shows 100% protection rate against persistent cervical infection and CIN. [18] According to CDC guidelines HPV vaccine can be offered to both male and female of ages 9-26years, whereas FDA recommends HPV vaccination till 45 years of age. [19,20]

Although many studies were conducted to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of cervical cancer screening among women in general population, studies on female healthcare professionals were very less. [21,22,23] In our country, women are more comfortable to discuss with female health care professionals than male counterpart due to traditional and religious beliefs. We therefore conducted this questionnaire based

study on female healthcare professionals to assess their knowledge, attitude and practices towards cervical cancer and screening.

Materials & Methods

This is a cross sectional study conducted at Obstetrics and Gynaecology department in Velammal Medical College and Research Institute, Madurai from January 2024 to June 2024 among the female healthcare professional's doctors, nurses and ANM.

All female employees belonging to the cadre of doctors, staff nurse ANM who were working in Velammal medical college and research institute were line listed. After obtaining the consent, the participants for the study were chosen by simple random sampling.

A standardized questionnaire was used to collect the required data which includes socio demographic characteristics, knowledge, attitude and practices towards cervical cancer screening. The study was approved by institutional ethical committee and involved about 332 participants. Professionals in OBG department were excluded from the study in order to avoid selection bias.

Sample Size Calculation: Sample size was calculated with the prevalence of 26.2% from the previous study.[24] Keeping α error at 5%and absolute precision of 5% with 95% CI and 10% non-response rate, the minimum sample size required was 332.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered in MS excel. Analysis was done using SPSS version 21.Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentage whereas continuous variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. Association between the variables were analyzed using Chi square test and expressed as odds ratio with 95% CI. p value ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

Totally 332 study participants were in our study .A total of 154, 100 and 78 study participants were doctors, staff nurses and ANM respectively. 174 study participants were ≤ 26 years of age. About 54.8% were married. 11.1% (37) participants reported history of carcinoma cervix among their relatives and friends. The following are the socio demographic characteristics of study participants.

Table 1: Distribution of study participants according to the Socio demographic Profile (n=332)

Characteristics		Frequency n=332	Percentage %
Age (in years)	< 30 years	239	72
	31 – 65 Years	92	27.7
	>65 Years	1	0.3
Education	High school/ Diploma	131	39.5
	Bachelor	151	45.5
	Professional/Master	50	15.1
Designation	Doctor	154	46.4
	Staff Nurse	100	30.1
	ANM	78	23.5
Years of Experience	< 1 year	133	40.1
	1 – 5 years	102	30.7
	6 – 20 years	87	26.2
	> 20 years	10	3
Marital Status	Married	182	54.8
	Unmarried	150	45.2
Age at Marriage n=182	18 – 25 years	134	40.3
	26 – 35 years	47	14.2
Number of Pregnancies (n=130)	1 – 2	107	32.3
	3 – 5	23	6.9
Number of Children n=165	1 – 2	159	47.9
	3	6	1.8
Number of Abortions n=69	1	54	16.3
	2 – 3	15	4.5
History of First Degree Relatives with Carcinoma Cervix		22	6.6
History of Second Degree Relatives or Friends with Carcinoma Cervix		15	4.5

Table 2: Distribution of study participants according to knowledge about Carcinoma Cervix (n=332)

Characteristics		Frequency (n=332)	Percent-age %
Risk Factors	Multiple sexual partners	194	58.4
	Early sexual intercourse	163	49.1
	HPV infection (human papilloma virus)	194	58.4
	HIV(Human immunodeficiency virus) infection	127	38.3
	Cigarette smoking	130	39.2
	Oral contraceptives	116	34.9
Vulnerability	Women age>50yrs	84	25.3
	Reproductive age	130	39.2
	Both of the above	118	35.5
Signs & symptoms	Vaginal bleeding	200	60.2
	Foul smelling vaginal discharge	190	57.2
	Contact bleeding	176	53
Prevention	Avoiding multiple sexual partners	283	85.2
	Avoiding early sexual intercourse	244	73.5
	Screening & treatment	258	77.7
	Avoid/Quit cigarette smoking	233	70.2
	All the above	242	72.9
Ways of screening	Pap smear	284	85.5
	Visual Inspection of cervix	235	70.8
	Human papilloma virus DNA testing	208	62.7
	Liquid based cytology	211	63.6
	There is no way for screening cancer cervix	30	9
Levels of Knowledge scoring	Poor Knowledge 0 – 4	32	9.6
	Fair Knowledge 5 – 10	69	20.8
	Good Knowledge 11 – 20	231	69.6

Table 3: Participants attitude towards cervical cancer (n = 332)

Characteristics	Agree n (%)	Neither agree nor disagree n (%)	Disagree n (%)
Ca cervix is highly prevalent and one of the leading cause of cancer death	258 (77.7)	25 (7.5)	49 (14.8)
Any young women including you can acquire cervical carcinoma	218 (65.7)	26 (7.8)	88 (26.5)
Ca cervix cannot be transmitted from one person to another	206 (62.0)	23 (6.9)	103 (31.0)
Screening helps in prevention of ca cervix	292 (88.0)	11 (3.3)	29 (8.7)
Screening causes no harm to the client	252 (75.9)	19 (5.7)	61 (18.4)
Screening for ca cervix is not expensive	235 (70.8)	25 (7.5)	72 (21.7)
If screening is free and causes no harm will you screen?	256 (77.1)	28 (8.4)	48 (14.5)

Table 4: Distribution of study participants according to Practice of Screening for Carcinoma Cervix (n=332)

Characteristics	Frequency (n=332)	Percentage %	
I have heard of PAP SMEAR test for cervical cancer screening	292	88	
Pap smear test is a useful tool for early detection of cervical cancer	301	90.7	
Age at which pap smear test to be started	From birth	4	1.2
	From Puberty	21	6.3
	From 21yrs	170	51.2
	From 31yrs	108	32.5
	After Menopause	29	8.7
I have undergone Pap smear test	53	16	
Why haven't you done the test	I find no reason for the test	179	53.9
	I'm afraid of the procedure	52	15.7
	I'm afraid of bad results	14	4.2
	I don't know whom to consult for undergoing this test	34	10.2
Interval for pap smear test	Yearly	79	23.8
	3 years once	130	39.2
	5 years once	51	15.4
	Not sure	72	21.7
Best time for doing pap smear	During periods or menses	16	4.8
	A week after period	265	79.8
	During pregnancy	3	0.9
	During Breast feeding	1	0.3
	Not sure	47	14.2
Pap smear test should be done by	Doctor	258	77.7
	Trained nurse	9	2.7
	Any of the above two	56	16.9
	Not sure	9	2.7
Any abnormality in pap smear report	Leave it to God & pray	0	0
	Further Investigation	291	87.7
	Not sure	21	6.3
	Others	20	6
Benefits of Pap smear test	Early detection of cervical cancer	82	24.7
	Detection of any abnormal changes in cervix	29	8.7
	Above 2	214	64.5
	Not sure	7	2.1
Pap smear test is painful	92	27.7	
Undergoing Pap smear test is a good practice	310	93.4	
Pap smear test is done using	Transvaginal ultrasound	42	12.7
	Vaginal brush	254	76.5
	Not sure	35	10.5
	Others	1	0.3

HPV vaccine available in our institution	No	71	21.4
	Yes	250	75.3
	Don't Know	11	3.3
I have been vaccinated for HPV	Yes	71	21.4
	No	261	78.6

Table 5: Association between Level of Knowledge and study participants either undergone PAP or HPV vaccination (n=332)

Knowledge Scoring	Practicing n=102(30.7%)	Not Practicing n=230(69.3%)	Odds Ratio	p value
Poor Knowledge (0-4)	5	27	2.58	0.05
Fair Knowledge (5 – 10) and Good Knowledge (11 – 20)	97	203		

p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Table 6: Association between Level of Knowledge and Practice among various designations (n=332)

Characteristics		Doctor n=154	Staff Nurse n=100	ANM n=78	Chi square	p value
Knowledge	Poor Knowledge (0-4)	2	5	25	99.18	0.001
	Fair Knowledge (5 – 10)	15	25	29		
	Good Knowledge (11 – 20)	137	70	24		
Practice	Undergone PAP smear test	17	27	9	13.002	0.002
	Undergone HPV Vaccination	26	32	13	9.592	0.008

Chi square value > 3.84 & p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Figure 1: Overall Knowledge Score

Figure 2: Participants agreed for attitude towards cervical cancer N(%)

Figure 3: Association between Practice and various designation

Figure 4: Association between level of knowledge and practice among various designation

Discussion

The Mean age of study participants was 28.65±7.2 years. Since there is a long time lag to convert into cancerous lesion from precancerous cervical lesion maximum screening awareness should be done in younger age group people.18 It has been already well known that cytological screening and HPV vaccination can reduce major burden of carcinoma cervix. [25,26]

Knowledge about cervical cancer: We have to understand about the knowledge, beliefs and perceptions of the population especially that of the healthcare staff because they are playing a vital role in propagation of health related information. Many similar studies conducted in developing countries

provide useful information to develop essential educational strategies. [27,28,29]

In our study 20.8% and 69.6% study participants had fair and good knowledge respectively. Especially doctors had good knowledge when compared to staff nurse & ANM. (P= 0.001). In a study conducted by Chawla et al health care professional had overall knowledge of about 75.14%. 33 But various studies conducted in UK, Hong Kong and China shows low level of knowledge about cervical cancer but they had higher knowledge level to participate in screening process. [30,31,32]

Attitude about cervical cancer and screening: 22.9% (n=76) participants disagreed to undergo

screening even when offered freely. Also 24% (n=80) disagreed the fact that screening does not cause any harm to the participants. 22.3% (n=74) study participants disagreed the fact the carcinoma cervix is one of the leading cause of death in our country. About 88% (n=292) study participants agreed that screening helps in prevention of carcinoma cervix in our study.

In a similar study by Humariya heena et al conducted in Saudi Arabia 3.8% (n=15) agreed for screening and only 4.6% (n=18) agreed that screening helps in prevention of cancer cervix which is in contrast to our study results. [24] In Sakrawal et al study, 95% women in rural population realized the seriousness of carcinoma cervix and 63% were willing to undergo the screening tests. [18]

Table 7: Association between number of study participant's ≤ 26 years of age and their vaccination status for HPV

Age in years	Taken HPV Vaccination	Not taken HPV vaccination
≤ 26 Years(174)	48(27.6%)	126(72.4%)
≥ 27 Years(158)	23(14.6%)	135(85.4%)

P value is 0.005, hence it is considered as significant.

In Chawla et al study 76.68% health professionals had knowledge of HPV but only 20.56% had undergone HPV vaccination which is comparable with our study. [33]

Conclusion

Our study concluded that even though our health care professionals had fair to good knowledge of cancer cervix, attitude towards screening is also appropriate, there is a very low practice towards screening and also HPV vaccination.

Hence we are in a need to sensitize our health care professionals because they play an essential role in implementation of future cervical cancer screening programme and HPV vaccination campaign among the general public therefore they should have their knowledge assessed and updated.

The current gap between knowledge and practice should be met by organized educational programs in order to promote female health and to create a healthier nation. The government should also be proactive in implementation of awareness campaigns and to include HPV vaccination in Indian immunization schedule.

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Practice about cervical cancer: In our study about 93.4% (n=310) of study participants agreed that undergoing pap testing is good practice. Also 64.5% (n=214) agreed carcinoma cervix can be diagnosed earlier by screening. 51.2% (n=170) agreed to do Pap smear from 21 years of age. 53.9% (n=179) study participants believed that there was no reason to undergo this screening test. Only 16% (n= 53) of our study participants had undergone Pap smear testing. 71 (21.4%) study participants had taken HPV vaccination of which 26 were doctors. Surprisingly 32 were staff nurses and 13 were ANM staffs.

Out of 71 participants who had HPV vaccination, 48 study participants were aged ≤ 26 years of age which is our target group for HPV Vaccination.

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